

Evaluation of innovations towards waste prevention across three demo cases

Deliverable 6.1

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plastic packaging value chain

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ABBREVIATIONS

BC: Beverage Carton
 CE: Circular Economy
 CIWMS: Circular Integrated Waste Management System
 EoL: End-of-Life
 EVOH: Ethylene Vinyl Alcohol
 HDPE: High Density PolyEthylene
 IS: Industrial Symbiosis
 LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
 LDPE: Low Density PolyEthylene,
 NIR: Near Infra-red
 PBSA: Polybutylene Succinate Adipate
 PE: Polyethylene
 PET: PolyEthylene Terephthalate
 PHA: Polyhydroxyalkanoates
 PHB: Polyhydroxybutyrate
 PLA: Polylactic Acid
 PP: polypropylene
 PS: polystyrene
 PVC: Polyvinyl chloride
 rPET= recycled PET or recycled PolyEthylene Terephthalate
 TPS: Thermoplastic starch

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SUMMARY

The main aim of this report is the characterization of the rejected fraction and the exploration of the potential improvements and recommendations, analysing the potential impacts that the innovative solutions proposed by the CIRC-PACK Demo Cases have in terms of waste prevention, recycling rates and landfill storage.

The effect of different innovations into the sorting process and improvements needed to maximise recovery and recycling is evaluated, including their impact on the rejection flow, eco-design and waste reduction.

Chapter 1: aim of the deliverable and its relation to other CIRC-PACK activities is explained.

Chapter 2: a detailed overview of a sorting plant model in Spain is provided, including step-by-step description of how waste enters and flows through the sorting plant. The purpose is to describe how and why certain materials are 'rejected' from the recycling process. The Spanish plant is also compared with other sorting plant models in Europe for additional context.

Chapter 3: the development of the assessment methodology - which is used to analyse the waste prevention and environmental impacts of the CIRC-PACK Demo Cases - is described.

Chapter 4: results of an analysis of the rejection fraction of two streams (end-of-line and film streams) are presented. The composition of the rejected fraction was analysed according to: requested and non-requested materials (i.e. materials which are recyclable, but had nevertheless been rejected, and materials which were rejected because they are not requested for collection); eco-design principles (including colour, format, label size and dimensions); and material format (meaning, the purpose of the rejected material, such as pots, caps, trays etc.);

Chapter 5: following the rejection analysis, recommendations are made for how to reduce rejected materials through eco-design solutions. Key barriers in packaging design are summarised, and the potential for CIRC-PACK innovations developed in Demo Case A and B to address these barriers are discussed. Also includes the potential reductions in the amount of landfilled or incinerated waste are evaluated.

Conclusion of all the chapters are summarized at the end of the document.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Aim of the deliverable

This deliverable tries to summarize the analyses done about the characterization of the rejected fraction and the exploration of the potential improvements and recommendations, evaluating the potential impacts that the innovative solutions proposed by the CIRC-PACK Demo Cases have in terms of waste prevention, recycling rates and landfill storage.

The effect of different innovations into the sorting process and improvements needed to maximise recovery and recycling is evaluated, including their impact on the rejection flow, eco-design and waste reduction.

Chapter two discusses the standardization of sorting plants and how this design is related with the rejection or loss of packaging waste materials. Chapter three analyses what has been done in the 3 Use Cases with all the data of the demonstrators from the point of view of "waste prevention" taking into account aspects of environmental improvement. Chapter four discusses the rejection reasons of the sorting plants thanks to extensive characterizations in plants detecting what and why has not been separated. Chapter five discusses the recommendations to reduce rejected materials through eco-design solutions and the potential reductions in the amount of landfilled or incinerated waste are evaluated.

1.2 Relation to other tasks

This deliverable is based on the information of the three demo cases (WP3, WP4 and WP5) analysing the possibility of ecodesign packaging applying previous project developments. In addition, this deliverable is based on the analysis of the task 6.2.

WP2 does not have information in terms of Waste Prevention.

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2 SORTING PLANTS MODELS

The rejected fraction of the plants hugely depends on the configuration and infrastructure of the different sorting plants. To better understand the sorting plants, this first chapter explains in detail one of the standards for the sorting plans (the one established in Spain for the 95 facilities receiving domestic light packaging financed by Ecoembes). In addition, the chapter explains the differences with other standards.

2.1 Spanish sorting-plants model

Waste treated in light weight packaging sorting plants in Spain is obtained from the selective collection of yellow containers, where citizens deposit domestic light packages. These are plastic, metal and food and drink carton packages and beverage carton. The containers contain impurities or unsolicited material which must be separated from the requested materials during the sorting process.

- **Requested materials:** HDPE (high density polyethylene), PET (polyethylene terephthalate), LDPE (low density polyethylene, generally in film form) and the mixed plastic fraction composed of materials made of PS (polystyrene), PP (polypropylene) and other plastics; also included aluminium and steel packages, as well as beverage cartons (hereinafter BC).
- **Unsolicited materials:** Cardboard, celluloses, P/C, low and high-density film plastics and other impurities such as glass, textile wood, non-packaging plastic, organic matter, other metals, etc.

Figure 1. Light weight packaging sorting plant. Source: ECOEMBES

The treatment process in a lightweight packaging sorting plant is divided into four main groups of operations:

- Reception and storage.
- Pre-treatment.
- Sorting of materials.
- Quality controls, adaptation of selected materials and rejected waste management.

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Figure 2. Outline of sorting process. Source: Elaborated by ECOEMBES

These operations will vary depending on the automation level of the sorting plants. Facilities are classified as automated or manual depending on how the material sorting operation is performed.

Figure 3. Diagram of the automated sorting process. Source: Elaborated by ECOEMBES

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Figure 4. Diagram of the manual sorting process. Source: Elaborated by ECOEMBES

2.1.1 Reception and storage operations

Scales for monitoring and weighing of collection vehicles: Vehicles with packaging waste collected from streets arrive at the sorting facility passing through access control and weighing (scales). In order to transport the collected material more efficiently, when the street collection vehicles need to travel great distances from the place of collection to the destination plant, it is convenient to unload the material at intermediate locations (transfer stations) for compacting and subsequent transport in larger containers, if possible and those facilities exist. In this case, the material arriving at the plant has a bigger density, which must be considered when sizing the treatment capacity of the facility.

Unloading area for transported waste: After weighing the vehicles and identifying their origin and schedule, they are led to the covered reception area where the transported waste is unloaded in the area or location indicated by the discharge and feeding operator.

Positioning and stacking of unloaded waste: The loading shovel stacks the unloaded waste vertically, optimising the surface available for storage prior to treatment. This process can

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include several components of bulky waste with sizes or shapes (as in mattresses, large packages, bicycles, etc.) that hinder the work and could affect the sorting equipment to be used. Using the loading shovel the operator must place these in a specific container located on this or another surface.

2.1.2 Pre-treatment operations

Primary feeding-dosing: The waste deposited in the reception area is collected with the loading shovel (unload yard) or grapple hook (pit), transferred and unloaded in the dosing feeder with variable speed and flow limiter, used to control the treatment flow rate.

Bulky waste sorting: Waste regularly supplied by the feeder is unloaded in a bulky waste sorting conveyor belt, where sorting operators select the materials which due to their size or shape are detrimental to subsequent treatments, such as film sheets, cardboard, EED waste, etc. The selected bulky materials (recoverable and non-recoverable) are stored in containers located under the sorting cabin for delivery to the recycler or the treatment rejects section.

Bag opener: Non-sorted waste is downloaded by the same sorting belt in a bag opening unit designed to extract the materials from the bags when they are ready for the remaining sorting operations.

Classification in trommel: In many cases, the components of the bags are subjected to a sieving process using a trommel or revolving sieve, which classifies the materials into three sizes:

- Fine components with a high content in organic and inert material.
- Intermediate components with a high content in recyclable packages.
- Large components or sieving rejects.

Figure 5. Classification in trommel by size to separate light weight packaging (underflow) from organic matter (fine waste underflow) and bulky waste (overflow). Source: ECOEMBES

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Classification in ballistic separator: The stream of intermediate size materials of the trommel, if that exist, or from the bag opener directly, if that doesn't exist, is subsequently subjected to ballistic classification according to size, shape and density, and again separated into three new material streams:

- Stream of heavy-rolling material formed by the majority of the heavy and/or rolling material, mainly packaging for liquids, metal packaging and beverage carton. This falls down the inclined slope of the ballistic separator.
- Stream of light flat materials, mainly formed by cardboard, paper and other film plastics with a flat or flattened shape that rise up the inclined plane of the separator.
- Stream of fine materials made up of fine material that could not be sieved in the trommel because it was attached to or blocked by other material, which falls through the mesh of the separator.

The amount of material reaching each of the three fractions will depend on the quality of the material introduced in the equipment. For examples, in facilities with 75-85% of requested material at the inlet, the classification performed by a ballistic separator is about 80% rolling material, 15% light flat material, and 5% fine material.

At facilities where the sorting operations are performed manually, the ballistic separator is not used. The material arriving from the trommel, if exists, is taken directly to the sorting cabin, where the operators sort the requested materials

Figure 6. Classification using the ballistic separator based on density in segregating light-flat material (film and P/C) from heavy rolling material (packages). Source: ECOEMBES

2.1.3 Sorting of materials operations

Primary feeding-dosing: The waste deposited in the reception area is collected with the loading shovel (unload yard) or grapple hook (pit), transferred and unloaded in the dosing feeder with variable speed and flow limiter, used to control the treatment flow rate.

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Pneumatic separation: The main objective of pneumatic separation is to clean film and paper from the rolling and light flat material streams, since these hinder the segregation of the remaining materials. The selected material is subjected to a manual quality control to separate impurities. It is subsequently stored to prepare it for dispatch (compaction).

Magnetic separation: The rolling material stream obtained from ballistic segregation is subjected to segregation of magnetic materials (steel) using over-band separators. Similarly, the fine material fraction from the trommel, if the plant is equipped with this equipment, and ballistic separator are subjected to magnetic material sorting before being sent to the rejected waste fraction.

Optical separation: The rolling material stream that has not been selected by pneumatic aspiration on this line nor by the magnetic separator is subjected to optical segregation by infra-red or colorimetry detectors to segregate the following requested materials:

- PET packaging
- HDPE packaging
- Beverage carton packaging
- Mixed plastic packaging.

To improve the performance and quality in the sorting of these materials, the magnetic and pneumatic sorting must take place prior to the optical separation.

Figure 7. Optical separators. Source: ECOEMBES

Induction separation: The stream of materials not sorted by the optical separation is subjected to a sorting of non-magnetic metals (aluminium) by an eddy current separator.

Figure 8. Induction separators remove aluminium material using eddy currents. Source: ECOEMBES

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Manual separation: Materials not selected in the rolling and light flat material streams converge on a belt in which they are subjected to manual sorting. The remaining unselected material is sent to the rejected waste fraction.

2.1.4 Quality control, material adaptation and rejected waste management operations

Quality control: Due to errors occurring in the different types of equipment, the selected packaging material contain impurities that reduce the purity of the final product. These impurities are removed through manual sorting. This operation is usually performed after the sorting of each of the recovered materials (PET, HDPE, beverage cartons and mixed plastics) before storing in silos for compaction. In other facilities, the quality control is performed before compaction, so that a single operator can perform the operation. The sorted impurities are sent to the rejected waste stream at the facility or, if they are requested materials, recirculated to previous points of the process for sorting.

Figure 9. Quality control of selected materials. Source: ECOEMBES

Temporary storage of selected materials: The selected materials are deposited in specific confined spaces for each one (intermediate storage silos) awaiting compaction operations. Storage silos are compartments sized according to the following parameters:

- Apparent density of each material
- Production of each selected material per shift
- Hourly capacity of the compacting press.

The extraction of the materials stored in the silos is performed using moving bases, conveyor belts or directly with a loading shovel, which evacuate them to the feeder of the baling press placed downstream. If the selected amount of any material is small (e.g. aluminium) the production is stored in auxiliary containers for subsequent compaction.

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Figure 10. Temporary storage of selected materials. Source: ECOEMBES

Compaction of selected materials: Materials stored temporarily in the containers are subsequently subjected to density increasing operations using baling presses, which produce bales with a density suitable for final storage and subsequent transport. A single properly sized press can bale the output of all selected materials (PET, HDPE, FILM, beverage cartons and mixed plastics) except metals, and particularly steel, which require different bale sizes and features as well as specific presses.

Rejected waste management at the facility: all sorting facility rejects are typically concentrated on a single output conveyor belt that discharges them at the evacuation point. Occasionally the fine materials current is discharged at different points from other rejected waste. Due to the low density of the rejected waste material, its volume needs to be adapted for an efficient disposal to the landfill. This can involve several alternative systems:

- Self-compacters.
- Static compacters.
- Rejected waste press.
- Containers (for low-volume facilities).

Transport of containers with rejects is performed using container vehicles to take them to processing sites (landfill or energy recovery).

Figure 11. The rejected waste material at the facility is compacted or stored in containers for delivery to the landfill. Source: ECOEMBES

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Differences among plants

The model presented is a standard designed in Spain to define the sorting plants for light packaging. Not all these plants follow the standard literally; there are differences among them. The operations in a sorting plant will vary depending on the automation level of the sorting plant. Find here some differences:

- There are facilities with discharge pit and facilities with unloading yard as a reception area.
- Treatment lines with discharge pit are feeded by grapple hooks.
- Treatment lines with unloading yard are feeded by loading shovel.
- There are some sorting plants with trommel.
- Size mesh of the ballistic separator used to vary between 50 and 70 mm.
- Some plants have incorporated optical separation for film.
- We can find a lot of different configuration of optical separator chains.
- Induction separation with a different intensity is used for the sorting of beverage carton packaging in some plants.
- The selected materials quality control is performance by an operator, mostly. However, we can find optical separator quality control

Figure 12. Classification Trommel: Divides the material stream into two or more categories according to grain size using specific size sieves. Source: ECOEMBES

2.2 Other European sorting-plants models

According to the Circular Economy Action Plan (EC, 2020), the Commission will propose to harmonise separate waste collection systems in all Europe. At the future, all the requested materials will be harmonised, so a European sorting-plant model should be established. In this subsection some other models in Europe regarding sorting-plants, in which the results could be extrapolated to some extent, are presented.

The typical sorting-plant model in Europe involves several similar sorting steps, as presented in the above Spanish example. These include manual dismantling and sorting by automated

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processes, separation according to density and size, and optical or magnetic separation. However, the exact process can vary according to consumer behaviour and collection systems. For example, in the Nordic countries, consumer behaviour and market availability mean that less beverage carton packaging (TetraPack) is used than in Spain, meaning there is no separate stream for this kind of packaging.

The collection system used in different countries has also had a large influence on the historical development of MRFs. When recyclable materials are collected in separate streams, this can reduce the number of sorting steps needed, or free up capacity to sort a greater number of types or grades. On the other hand, mixed collection of recyclables saves resources at the front end but require a higher degree of technical complexity in MRFs (Cipram et al, 2015).

In general, there are four main collection models applicable in Europe (Lorenzo et al, 2016):

1. Single-stream collection: all dry recyclables (plastic, metal, paper, cardboard, and sometimes glass) are collected together. For instance, this is the main collection model in Greece, Ireland, Malta and Romania.
2. Dual-stream collection: 'fibres' (paper and cardboard) and 'non-fibre' (i.e. plastic, metal and glass) are collected separately. This is the main collection system in the Finland and the UK.
3. Mono-stream collection: each material is collected separately (i.e. paper and cardboard, glass, and lightweight packaging), and treated in a MRF. The Spanish model described above fits in this category. This collection system is the most prevalent in Europe, being applied in Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia and Sweden. In addition, some countries further separate the lightweight packaging stream into its constituent parts, including Austria, Denmark and the Netherlands.
4. Mixed Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) collection scheme: no separate collection of recyclables. This leads to high contamination rates and need for intensive treatment. While the Waste Framework Directive ([2008/98/EC](#)) required separate collection of paper, metal, plastic and glass from household waste by 2015, and 50% preparation for re-use and recycling by 2020, 14 Member States were identified as being at risk of missing this target. Ineffective separation of recyclables was cited as a contributing factor in 11 countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Estonia, Greece, Latvia, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, and Slovakia) (European Commission, 2019).

In practice, however, the collection and sorting model may vary widely within countries, as decision-making powers on the selection and operation of waste collection systems usually sits with local authorities.

Single-stream MRF example: Ford MRF Plant, West Sussex, UK

The comingling of fibres and lightweight packaging streams requires additional sorting steps to the Spanish example detailed above.

The Ford MRF Plant in the UK is an example of an advanced single-stream MRF. In operation since 2009, it was designed to process 100,000 tonnes per annum of comingled

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recyclables, including glass, based on a three-shift operation with 13 manual sorters per shift (Cimpan et al, 2015).

Conditioning operations: Upon reception, bags containing co-mingled recyclables are opened and fed to the input line. The material is conveyed to a pre-sorting cabin, where items which could damage equipment such as large cardboard, metals, and plastic foils is manually removed.

Next, a primary separation process is performed in a two-section drum, in order to pre-concentrate materials and break glass into smaller pieces. Most glass is sorted out in the first section which separates ‘fines’ (under 75mm). The second section separates a mixed stream of paper and containers, which is then sent to a double-deck ballistic separator, which separates 3D items (containers) from 2D items (paper). Another stream of fines is also separated at this stage and joined to the fines from primary separation. A stream of trommel overflow or ‘oversized’ items remains.

Sorting of materials operations: Out of the initial sorting described above, four material streams emerge:

1. Oversize: this needs to be cleaned in order to produce its main output - newspaper and magazines - using NIR to remove cardboard and plastics, followed by manual quality control. The output from the NIR is further split by a second NIR into cardboard (which is joined to the 2D stream) and plastic (which is processed using a second ballistic separator to recover any containers for the 3D stream). Any remaining 2D material is classed as sorting residue.
2. 2D stream: ferrous and non-ferrous components are removed using magnetic and eddy current separation. It passes through a NIR for a final clean before it arrives at manual quality control. Material removed in the NIR is sent to the second ballistic separator to recover any containers.
3. 3D stream: ferrous and non-ferrous components are removed using magnetic and eddy current separation. It passes through a NIR which removes cardboard and paper (returned to the 2D line), manual quality control, before being flattened and entering the polymer sorting block. NIR sorting divides it into clear PET, coloured PET, natural HDPE and coloured HDPE. The leftover passes a final NIR sorter which removes any missed polymers, which are recirculated to the beginning of the 3D line.
4. Fines stream: ferrous and non-ferrous components are removed using magnetic and eddy current separation. It then passes through screening, air density separation and a final NIR sort, resulting in an output of clean glass cullet product (>12mm).

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Figure 13. Ford MRF Plant, West Sussex, UK. Source: Cimpan et al, 2015

Mono-stream MRF example: Germany

In Germany, 'Yellow bags' collect a wide range of packaging waste including plastics (including films), cans, and cartons. Glass and paper are collected separately. In addition, large volumes of PET bottles are returned by consumers separately under the German 'pfand' system. Without the challenge of separating fibres from containers, MRFs in countries

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with separate collection have developed to handle larger volumes of very light waste (Cipman et al. 2015).

Approximately 2.25 million tonnes of packaging are collected each year, 90% of which is sorted in less than 50 plants, with a high level of standardisation in process design (Cipman et al. 2016). The most advanced plants can have up to 20 NIR sorting machines, plus additional sensing equipment such as ultrasonic or VIS-camera based volume flow measurement devices (Cipman et al. 2015).

Conditioning operations: as a first step, yellow bags are coarsely shredded. Materials are then sieved using drum screens (trommels), in order to sort them into workable sizes for the downstream equipment. Plastic films are separated using an air classifier.

Materials smaller than 220 mm are further separated into two or four further particle size intervals. The main mass flow (20-220 millimetres) represents 80-85% of the input stream and is processed on two or three individual lines. Air classification is used to further separate plastic films (10%), to improve downstream sensor sorting. Next suspension magnets separate ferromagnetic materials (9-13% of the input stream). NIR sensors are then used to separate beverage cartons, before non-ferrous components are separated using eddy currents (mostly aluminium, <5% input).

Next, two more NIR steps separate paper/ card packaging and all plastics. The mixed plastic is then further cleaned using ballistic separators to remove fines and any remaining 2D material before entering polymer sorting, where plastics are sorted into HDPE, PP, PET and PS. A second cleaning step or colour sorting (for PET) may also then take place, in addition to a final NIR to detect missed polymers and recirculate them to the beginning of the polymer sorting block.

Figure 14. Typical German sorting model. Source: Cimpan et al, 2015

Complete source separation MRF example: Kruschitz PET reprocessing centre, Völkermarkt, Austria

In systems where lightweight packaging is separated into its constituent parts at source, specialised sorting facilities are possible. Völkermarkt has been specialised in PET recycling since 2003 and produces food-grade regranulate in its 'bottle-to-bottle' plant (Kruschitz Plastics and Recycling, no date).

PET bottles arrive at the plant in bales, where they are opened and shredded, and passed through a ballistic separator. The PET stream then passes through an NIR separator, and a secondary shredder further reduces flakes to 12mm. Flakes are pre-washed and sorted using a density sorting/ flotation technique to sort out capsules and other impurities. The PET

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is then hot washed with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to remove labels, and waste water from this process is microfiltrated to clean out the glue. The PET passes through a vacuum reactor to clean it of any organic contaminants, and is finally dried and goes to the extruders, where the PET is melted and pressed through a cone to produce long strings of plastic, which can then be cut into pellets.

As a result, the purity of the resulting secondary PET output can reach 99.9%, with maximum impurities of 100-200 ppm (Neidel and Jakobsen, 2013).

Croatian sorting-plant model Marišćina

With the establishment and development of the packaging waste management system, many companies have modernised their existing, or have built new facilities for waste recovery using EPEEF subsidies. Even though new facilities have been built, and a number of existing ones has been improved, i.e. the capacities for packaging waste recovery have been increased, especially plastic packaging, considering that the market for packaging materials is rapidly evolving, an improvement of the existing technology will be necessary, in terms of the technological applicability for the treatment of some types of packaging waste, e.g. for certain types of multilayer (composite) packaging. Capacities for treatment of packaging containing remains of hazardous matter or being polluted by hazardous matter are, on a national level, insufficient, so it is mostly exported from the RC. Despite the positive direction in packaging waste management, there exists a need for the improvement of the mechanism of data supervision for the quantity of produced packaging waste, as well as the data on efficiency of recovery (recycling) and the improvement of systems for certain materials (e.g. for packaging except beverage packaging), and the need to establish a packaging waste management system for packaging that contains the remains of hazardous matter or that is polluted by hazardous matter. The existing packaging waste management system does not sufficiently encompass all the types of packaging waste.

Similarities with Spanish sorting-plant model:

Packaging waste in Croatia is collected in yellow containers (or containers with yellow lids) placed in public places and in the recycling yards. Usable material disposed in yellow containers are:

- o polyethylene bags, foils, films, bubble wrap – they need to carry the following labels: PE-HD, PE-LD, PET, PP, etc.;
- o bottles of edible oil, distilled water, cleaning and washing agents, cosmetics, medicines (except cytostatics), foodstuffs, etc. - labels: PE-HD, PE-LD, PP, etc.;
- o glasses and jars of yogurt, cheese, etc. – with designation: PS, PP, etc.;
- o packaging for various food products made of polystyrene (styrofoam) - with the EPS mark, etc.;
- o multilayer packaging (carton for beverages),
- o other plastic products: refreshment bottles, stoppers, plastic plates, cutlery, etc. – with following labels: PE-HD, PP, PVC, PS, PET, etc.;
- o food cans and beverage cans.

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The treatment process of packaging waste is similar with Spanish sorting plant (reception and storage, pre-treatment, sorting of materials, quality controls, adaptation of selected materials and rejected waste management).

Reception and storage: Packaging waste, collected through containers, is delivered to facility by cargo trucks. Upon acceptance of the waste, the mass of the waste received is determined and these data are recorded in the register of each type of waste received. After a visual inspection of the waste, the waste is unloaded from the truck and dumped in the waste storage facility according to waste categorization - types of polymer material, in primary tanks, bales or in piles.

Pre-treatment operation: After the waste is inspected and categorized, it is separated and stored according to the type of polymeric material and the type of packaging in which it is received, to prevent dust, noise, odors and other emissions from spreading. Transport of waste to and from storage is carried out by forklifts and with hand pallet trucks.

Sorting of materials, quality controls, adaptation of selected materials: The waste deposited in the reception area is collected with forklifts and delivered to the recovery line. The waste is fed into the inlet tank and then transported to the mill/crusher with vertical conveyor with the inlet feeder.

The mill/crusher shreds the waste into a 14 mm size fraction. The aim of shredding is to obtain a waste that is easier to clean in the further process of washing and cleaning the waste material.

The crawler conveyor located at the outlet of the mill/crusher, transports the shredded plastic fractions to the centrifuge-operated washing machine. The centrifuge machine is used to clean the polymer material in such a way that at high speed, using centrifugal force, separation of impurities (less than 3 mm) from the polymer fraction occurs. Impurities such as dust or mud are separated by a perforated sieve.

After cleaning the waste in the centrifuge machine, the crushed and purified waste material enters the hydroseparation machine. In the hydroseparation machine, the waste material is immersed and cleaned with water, but the hydroseparator also serves to sort the waste. The plastic fraction as a lighter material floats to the surface and is transferred to the centrifuge machine via water and portable blades. Contaminants (heavier fraction) such as stones, metal, etc. end up at the bottom of the hydro separator. After the drying, waste is transported to the storage silos. Waste is then pressed into bales and suitable for further transport.

Rejected waste management: All the material that is not suitable for the recycling is transported to one of the Mechanical Biological Treatment Facilities in Croatia. The process of mechanical-biological treatment of mixed municipal waste begins with accepting the same in the receiving pit within the MBT building, after which the waste is shredded with primary shredder and the bio-drying boxes are filled. When they have completed the biological drying process, which takes approximately 7-8 days, so that the waste is stabilized, it is extracted from the pits and moved to a mechanical treatment, where the fraction of 0-25 mm is first separated on the vibratory sieve, then the iron is separated and then nonferrous metals. The following is the separation of inert heavy fractions by air separator, followed by

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the separation of PVC by optical separators. Waste is then shredded on the secondary shredders and thus it becomes SRF or RDF.

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3 DEMO CASES ANALYSIS IN TERMS OF WASTE PREVENTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPROVEMENT

3.1 Literature Review

3.1.1 Scope

Waste prevention assessment of demo cases activities under Task 6.1 were initiated with a literature review on waste prevention and circularity studies for developing assessment methodology. Literature review aimed:

- To survey waste prevention and circular economy relations
- To develop quantification methodology of waste prevention
- To review indicators used for evaluating waste prevention actions
- To survey EoL option percentages which are currently used in Europe for plastic waste packaging
- To survey EoL options for biobased plastics

3.1.2 Method

Articles related to waste prevention concept, links between waste prevention and circularity and measurement of waste prevention were surveyed. Since targets for preventing of waste have come to the forefront in recent years, there have been different arguments in the literature reviewed. Over 60 articles and reports were scanned and 12 of them were examined in detail during literature review.

Firstly, information about waste prevention concept was searched for linking to circular economy approach. Then, measuring methods in the literature studies were scanned to develop methodology of waste prevention evaluation. In addition to these, EoL options were researched for plastic packaging waste and bioplastic waste.

3.1.3 Reviewed Literature

Waste management options are ordered in the waste hierarchy, defined in Article 3 of the Waste Framework Directive, according to their environmental impacts. The first option of hierarchy is waste prevention. EU waste hierarchy is given in the Figure 15 (European Commission, 2012).

Figure 15. EU waste hierarchy (European Commission, 2012)

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Any precautions taken before a substance, material and product become waste are expressed as waste prevention. With waste prevention, **reduction of waste amount, negative impacts of the generated waste and the content of harmful substances in materials and products are targeted** (Cobo, Dominguez-Ramos, & Irabien, 2018).

Not only waste management sector but also productive industries, service providers and consumers are related to waste prevention programme. Scope of waste prevention is shown in the Figure 16 (European Commission, 2012).

Figure 16. Waste prevention scope (European Commission, 2012)

Waste prevention is seen as effective option for reducing plastic waste and environmental effects of it. Environmental issues related to the plastic waste are expressed as shown in the below Figure 17 (EEA, 2019). By applying waste prevention activities, mentioned environmental issues can be prevented.

Figure 17. Environmental issues in plastic value chain (EEA, 2019)

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Plastic wastes are seen as important due to high production and use amounts in a lot of sectors. Plastic and packaging waste have been prioritized in waste prevention programmes of 20 countries. In some programmes of countries, these waste types were not mentioned as priority waste stream, but they were addressed. The list of countries is given in Figure 18 (EEA, 2019).

Austria		Luxembourg	
Belgium (Brussels-Capital Region)		Malta (*)	
Belgium (Flanders)		Netherlands (*)	
Belgium (Wallonia)		Norway (*)	
Bulgaria (*)		Poland	
Croatia		Portugal	
Czechia		Romania	
Denmark		Slovakia	
Estonia		Slovenia	
Finland		Spain	
France		Sweden	
Germany		Switzerland	
Greece		Turkey	
Hungary		United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) (*)	
Iceland		United Kingdom (Scotland)	
Ireland (*)		United Kingdom (England)	
Italy (*)		United Kingdom (Wales)	
Latvia (*)		Cyprus	n/a
Lithuania			

■ Packaging or plastics mentioned as priority waste stream/priority sector
■ Packaging or plastics may be addressed but not mentioned as priority waste stream/priority sector

Notes: (*) No data available based on Eionet survey; data obtained based on desktop research
 n/a, data not available.

Figure 18. Country list prioritized of plastic or packaging waste (EEA, 2019)

Better resource management and waste prevention are included in circular economy concept. Circular economy concepts are adopted by the EC in 2015. As 2030 targets, important actions are identified. Reduction of municipal solid waste to 10% is specified as landfill restriction target. Although highest priority is on the waste prevention at source, there is no quantitative waste prevention targets (except for food waste) in EU legislation. It is stated that current and future waste flows are needed to develop innovative waste management and implement CE models. Detailed waste generation, collection and treatment data are required (Zeller, Towa, Degrez, & Achten, 2018).

There is link between industrial symbiosis and Circular Integrated Waste Management Systems (CIWMSs) in terms of resource exchange network. It is stated that IS play a major role in the circular economy by providing waste exchange between facilities. However, CIWMS concept is more comprehensive than IS. In the concepts, not only industrial systems but also waste managers, consumers and supply chains are covered (Cobo et al., 2018).

In the literature, LCA approach was used for evaluating waste prevention (Cobo et al., 2018, Cristobal Garcia, Vila, Giavini, Torres De Matos, & Manfredi, 2016, Nessi, Rigamonti, & Grosso, 2012, Matsuda et al., 2018, Nessi, Rigamonti, & Grosso, 2014, Cánovas Creus, Bernstad Saraiva, & Arruda, 2018, Gentil, Gallo, & Christensen, 2011). In addition to LCA approaches, change in waste generation amount with the application of waste prevention activities was investigated by using indicators (Zeller et al., 2018, EEA, 2019). In the waste prevention programmes, some indicators are used for assessment of plastic waste prevention. The list of indicators according to countries is as shown in the Figure 19.

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Country	Indicator
Indicators relating to the amount of plastic waste/plastic packaging waste (*)	
Belgium (Brussels-Capital Region)	Volume of household packaging waste (kg)
Denmark	Trends in the amount of packaging and the proportion of packaging that is collected for recycling and recovery
Estonia	Growth rate of packaging waste generation in relation to the growth rate of gross domestic product
Lithuania	Quantity of packaging placed on the domestic market (per capita)
Poland	Quantity of packaging waste (kg) in relation to the volume of products put on the market (kg)
Slovakia	Amount of packaging waste generated and ratio of plastic packaging waste to amount of plastic packaging put on the market
Spain	Amount of packaging waste generated per year
Indicators relating to the reuse of plastics/ plastic packaging	
Greece	Percentage of reusable plastic packaging
Iceland (°)	The proportion of reusable beverage packaging in total packaging bearing a recycling deposit
Indicators relating to the introduction of deposit fees	
Germany	Amount of returnable (reusable) beverage packaging
Iceland (°)	Proportion of beverage packaging for which customers can receive a recycling deposit in the total amount of beverage packaging
Indicators relating to the number of implemented measures for plastic waste prevention	
Greece	Number of awareness raising events
Italy (°)	Number of signed agreements to promote points of sale of loose/bulk products and number of businesses that sell loose/bulk products
	Number of information campaigns created to encourage the consumption of tap water instead of bottled water
	Number of programme agreements to encourage the use of tap water
Sectoral indicators	
United Kingdom (England)	Amount of packaging waste in grocery supply chains
Indicators referring to the use of plastic carriers bags	
Bulgaria (°)	Amount of used polymer bags
Croatia	Number of bags put on the market
Iceland (°)	Number of new plastic carrier bags made per year
Romania	Number of shopping bags
Slovenia	Number of plastic bags (very lightweight plastic carrier bags are excluded)
Switzerland	The percentage reduction of lightweight plastic bags compared with a reference year (based on a voluntary agreement of the retailers)
Turkey	Consumption of single-use carrier bags
United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) (°)	Consumption of single-use carrier bags

Figure 19. Plastic waste prevention indicators in waste prevention programmes (EEA, 2019)

In CIRC-PACK, analysing biobased plastic usage in plastic packaging sector is one of the studied demo cases. According to biobased plastic types, different EoL options can be implemented. In the literature, studies related to EoL options of different biobased plastic waste were carried out. In one of them, EoL options were evaluated according to different use cases. Summary of the investigation of these options are given in Table 1. Disposal options vary depending on whether they are compostable or not.

Table 1. Investigated EoL options of biobased plastic (COWI A/S & Utrecht University, 2019)

EoL Options of Biobased Plastic					
Case Study	Biobased Plastic Type	Landfilling	Recycling	Incineration	Composting
Beverage Bottles	Biobased PET	✓	✓	✓	
	PET	✓	✓	✓	
Single Use Clips	Biobased starch	✓		✓	
	PP	✓		✓	

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EoL Options of Biobased Plastic					
Case Study	Biobased Plastic Type	Landfilling	Recycling	Incineration	Composting
Single Use Cups for Cold Drinks	Biobased PLA	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Biobased PP	✓	✓	✓	
	PP	✓	✓	✓	
	PET	✓	✓	✓	
Single Use Cutlery	Biobased PLA Mix	✓		✓	✓
	PS	✓	✓	✓	
Agricultural Mulching Film	Biobased starch	✓		✓	
	LDPE	✓	✓	✓	
Food Packaging Film	Biobased PLA	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Biobased PP	✓	✓	✓	
	PP	✓	✓	✓	
Single Use Carrier Bags	Biobased LDPE	✓	✓	✓	
	Biobased Starch	✓		✓	✓
	LDPE	✓	✓	✓	

In another research, which EoL options were examined for different biobased plastic waste in how many studies are summarized. In Table 2, result of this examination are given.

Table 2. Number of research study for EoL options of biobased plastic waste types (Spierling et al., 2018)

EoL Options of Biobased Plastic					
Plastic Types	Number of Research Study				
	Mechanical Recycling	Chemical Recycling	Industrial Composting	Incineration	Landfill
PLA	9	5	11	9	7
PHB	-	-	-	1	-
PLA-Mix	1	-	1	1	-
TPS-Blend	4		5	4	3
Bio-PE	1	-	1	1	-
TPS	-	-	1	1	1
PBSA	1	1	-	1	1
Bio-PET	1	-	1	-	-
PHA	-	-	1	1	1

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In the light of literature review, assessment of waste prevention methodology has been developed within the scope of CIRC-PACK project. As abovementioned, waste prevention concept not only covers reduction in waste generation at source, but also includes prevention of negative impacts of generated waste and content of harmful substances in materials or products. Therefore, within the scope of waste prevention assessment methodology for CIRC-PACK, biobased polymer usage instead of fossil based resources as less harmful substances and negative impacts to the environment (DC-A), different eco-design solution (DC-B) and improvement in recycling processes of plastic packaging waste (DC-C) are evaluated by taking into consideration quantitative change in waste generation amount and different EoL options due to innovative applications.

3.2 Assessment of Waste Prevention

3.2.1 Methodology

As stated in the literature review, any precautions taken before a substance, material and product become waste are expressed as waste prevention. Also, reduction of negative impacts of generated waste and harmful substances in products are aimed in waste prevention approach. These aims include biobased compostable plastic use, recycling of plastics and eco-design solutions. In this project, reduction of waste amount sent to landfill or incineration was considered as waste prevention.

Waste prevention assessment methodology of demo cases is developed by using some indicators. The assessment methodology was initiated with analysing of CIRC-PACK demo cases and value chains in terms of waste generation and EoL options.

In the CIRC-PACK, different plastic packaging value chains are analysed. According to biobased plastic usage, find here the value chains and the demo cases evaluated specifically for value chains in waste prevention assessment:

1. Multi-material packaging powder detergent (*Biobased compostable bioplastic*) (DC-A and DC-B)
2. Shampoo bottles (*Biobased biodegradable bioplastic*) (DC-A)
3. Plastic bags (*Biobased biodegradable bioplastic*) (DC-A and DC-C)
4. Food trays (*Biobased biodegradable bioplastic*) (DC-A and DC-B)
5. Automotive components (*Fossil based plastic*) (DC-C)
6. Coffee capsules (*Biobased biodegradable bioplastic*) (DC-A and DC-C)
7. AHPs (*Biobased biodegradable bioplastic*) (DC-A, DC-B and DC-C)

In the assessment, baseline and CIRC-PACK implementations are compared in terms of waste prevention, in line with the EoL scenarios developed and worked under T2.4. The amount of waste sent to different EoL options (landfill, incineration, recycling, composting) was taken into consideration. In addition to evaluation of change in quantities, results of LCA obtained from T2.4 were included in the assessment by using inventory data.

Circularity assessment indicators are also analysed for both baseline and innovations. Evaluation of mass inventory for circularity assessment is carried out by taking into account of change in the amount of different materials. Materials which are related to waste prevention are as follows:

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1. User and product material to recycle
2. Wastes from end user
3. Wastes from sorting/recycling
4. Compostable wastes

These materials are used during the assessment stage. Whether CIRC-PACK project can contribute to waste prevention approach is determined by obtaining results from difference between baseline and CIRC-PACK innovations for these materials.

After that, circularity assessment indicators are evaluated in terms of waste prevention for value chains. The selected assessment indicators are:

1. Product mass
2. Linear flow index
3. Compostable rate
4. Wastes

3.2.2 Results of Assessment

Sorting process of waste is an important stage since sorted waste and rejected waste from sorting process can be sent to different EoL options which add value to wastes. In other words, sorting efficiency of waste types is directly related to EoL options in terms of managed waste quantity by these options. Relationship between sorting and EoL options contributes to evaluate waste prevention assessment.

In CIRC-PACK innovations, an adaptation of the current Near Infra Red (NIR) sorting systems were done in order to improve sorting efficiency of biobased plastic waste. Since biopolymer usage is one of the innovative solutions developed in the project, different behaviour of different plastic waste types in the sorting efficiency is highly important. Current situation data, provided by CALAF in Table 3, and CIRC-PACK value chains were firstly compared in terms of sorting efficiency. CALAF stated that the data were calculated under certain conditions mostly set by the limitations of NIR technology. The data was given in the basis of material types. The data was not specifically given for value chains in CIRC-PACK. Therefore, preliminary assessment was done in order to categorize material types according to CIRC-PACK value chains. Coffee capsules composed of PP were not presented in data table due to lack of data for PP material type. In CIRC-PACK, because fossil based plastic sorting, closed-loop recycling and use in automotive components is carried out inhouse, both baseline and innovations, this value chain leaves out of evaluation of sorting efficiency.

Table 3. Sorting data taken from CALAF for current situation. Source: CALAF

MATERIAL	VC in CIRC-PACK	RECOVERY (%)	PURITY (%)
PET	Shampoo bottle and food trays	94	94
		94	94
		94	96
PE	Plastic bags and powder detergent	95	98
Plastic Mix	-	92	94

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Tetra Pak	-	92	90
Film	AHPs	95	85

CALAF studied on sorting of biobased plastic waste developed in the project. According to the result of this study, sorting effectiveness and purity values are as given in Table 4.

Table 4. Sorting results of biobased plastic waste and variation according to current situation

	Value Chains							
	Bottles	Variation	Trays	Variation	Film	Variation	Coffee capsules	Variation
Presence of 3% Biobased Plastic Waste								
PURITY (%)	96.81	2.14	95.58	0.91	95.24	10.24	-	-
EFFECTIVENESS (%)	81.25	-12.75	96.43	2.43	100	5.00	-	-
Presence of 5% Biobased Plastic Waste								
PURITY (%)	96.54	1.87	98.20	3.53	92.96	7.96	-	-
EFFECTIVENESS (%)	84.29	-9.71	98.80	4.80	97.06	2.06	-	-
Presence of 10% Biobased Plastic Waste								
PURITY (%)	98.02	3.35	96.68	2.01	84.75	-0.25	88	-
EFFECTIVENESS (%)	81.95	-12.05	96.39	2.39	98.04	3.04	45	-

Comparison results of sorting effectiveness and purities are given in Table 4. Considering the result of CALAF's study, different presence of biobased plastic waste was incorporated into comparison with current situation. While lower sorting effectiveness was achieved in biobased bottles, higher effectiveness was obtained in biobased trays and films. However, purity showed a change according to value chains and presence of biobased plastic waste. In general, higher purity was observed in three value chains of CIRC-PACK innovation except for films with presence of 10% biobased plastic waste. As a result, and in general, higher sorting effectiveness can be achieved by bioplastic waste with appropriate sorting systems in tray and film value chains. Therefore, new plastic material type in bottle, trays and film value chains can be effectively sorted and sent to EoL options which add value to the waste.

According to the amount of sorted waste sent to different EoL option, results evaluations are given below for value chains whose data acquisition was completed until now. This part was done by using life cycle inventory data. Detailed data of the evaluation are given in Annex A.

In the light of the inventory results for powder detergent value chain, it can be stated that with the application of innovations, recycling of cardboard boxes in a regular recycling paper process can be achieved. In addition to this result, in primary packaging of box, the weight of the innovative box is 12% greater than the conventional one, and it requires 5.20% more electricity consumption during its manufacturing process. According to LCA results of EoL options studied in D2.4, recycling CIRC-PACK boxes is stated as the best scenario. With the use of new boxes, 24% less greenhouse gases can be achieved. On the other hand, if

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new boxes are not collected, sorted, recycled and sent to landfill or incineration, there is higher environmental impact than traditional PE laminated boxes. Therefore, collection, sorting and recycling processes are crucial.

In the automotive components value chain, while 100% incineration, 100% landfill and 100% recycling were considered as EoL scenarios, only 100% recycling was studied as EoL option for innovation case. CIRC-PACK aims to internally recycle the waste amounts in this value chain. When inventory data of the value chain is examined, it is seen that there is no change in terms of the amount of recycled PP. In the innovation, performed location of recycling process and the closed loop application of the recovered materials are aimed. When internally recycling is carried out in CRF, 100% of waste PP can be recycled. There is no change in recycled waste amount according to baseline and innovation data. Since fossil-based plastic is used in both baseline and innovation, composting is not considered as EoL option.

Within the scope of CIRC-PACK project, biobased compostable plastic use was carried out in food trays value chain. The results of food trays manufacturing show that the use of biopolymer material increases the tray's weight by 1% and the amount of rejects regenerated during the manufacturing process up to 5 % with respect to the baseline PET tray. If biopolymer-based trays are not well managed at the end of their lifetime, they can cause greater environmental impacts than the conventional ones. Differently from landfill and incineration, composting and biopolymer recycling can be implemented as EoL options due to biobased polymer usage in innovation case. In the LCA results obtained from Task 2.4, fossil-based PET has more environmental impact than biobased compound. Approximately 40% environmental improvement can be achieved by using biopolymer in food trays. It is stated that recycling is the best EoL option in terms of environmental impact. However, recycling of biopolymers has some limitations. It is suggested that number of recycling cycles of biopolymers should be one. After recycling, composting was recommended as second option.

Biobased compostable polymer usage in coffee capsules is investigated in CIRC-PACK. According to inventory results, composting is a new option compared to baseline. In baseline, 44% of the coffee capsule waste is sent to incineration and 56% of it is sent to landfill. However, incinerated and landfilled amount can be reduced to 17.6% and 22.4% respectively by using new polymer in order to produce capsules due to composting option. LCA results showed that environmental preferability of new coffee capsules is more than traditional capsules. In the LCA study, disposal of coffee was included in the system since separation of coffee from the waste capsules is not the preferable scenario due to the high required electric consumption. Therefore, coffee could be evaluated as avoided waste amount.

In plastic packaging for liquid shampoo value chain, there is 1% increase in the weight of shampoo bottle with biopolymer compared to conventional one. Differently from baseline, composting is one of the EoL option in innovation cases. According to LCA results, landfilling of biobased shampoo bottle has the highest impact. On the other hand, lower impact is obtained by composting bioplastics compared to fossil-based bottles. Environmental impact can be reduced up to 48% for some indicators by recycling of biobased bottle. Use

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of alternative raw material source and recycling of the products composed of alternative raw material source contribute to obtain environmental benefits.

In plastic bags value chain, weight of new biopolymer bags is 29% higher than PELD bags since new product has higher material density. Although landfilling, recycling and incineration are considered as EoL options for fossil-based bags, composting is included in addition to baseline options due to use of biobased compostable material. Plastic bags were investigated as **thin** and **thick** bags. LCA results show that incineration of new thin bags is the worst EoL option. On the other hand, impacts due to landfilling and composting are found similar. By recycling, important environmental improvement is provided because of reduction in new biopolymer production. However, it is stated that 30% recycled biopolymer use is acceptable for manufacturing new plastic bags by Mi-Plast.

As mentioned in the methodology section, indicator based assessment was also carried out for value chains during waste prevention assessment. Firstly, materials were evaluated in terms of waste prevention. According to this evaluation, circularity assessment indicators were examined. Baseline and innovation cases were taken into consideration in the assessment process. In Table 6 and Table 7, results of indicator based assessment were given.

Table 5. Waste prevention assessment according to materials

WASTE PREVENTION ASSESSMENT BY MATERIAL ANALYSIS						
Material	Value Chains					
	Powder Detergent	Automotive Components	Food Trays Manufacturing	Coffee Capsules	Packaging of Liquid Shampoo	Plastic Bags
User material to recycle	Recycling of boxes is achieved by innovations.	Internally recycling is improved by innovations.	Biopolymer recycling is provided by innovations.	Recycling is not considered as EoL options for innovation case.	Biobased bottle recycling is provided by innovations.	Recycling of biobased bags is provided by innovations.
Wastes from end user	Mass of unrecoverable waste through a product's material going to landfill is decreased by enabling the recyclability of the multimaterial.	Mass of unrecoverable waste through a product's material going to landfill is decreased by improving recycling.	Mass of unrecoverable waste through a product's material going to landfill is decreased by using biobased compostable raw material.			
Wastes from sorting/ recycling	Sorting efficiency is improved by innovation case. The waste amount is decreased.	Recycling efficiency is improved by in house closed loop recycling.	Sorting efficiency is improved by innovation case. The waste amount is decreased.	-	Sorting efficiency is decreased by innovation case. The waste amount is increased.	Sorting efficiency is improved by innovation case. The waste amount is decreased.
Compostable waste	Biobased compostable waste is generated.	There is no biodegradable waste due to fossil based raw material use.	Biobased biodegradable waste is generated.			

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Table 6. Waste prevention assessment according to circularity assessment indicators

WASTE PREVENTION ASSESSMENT BY CIRCULARITY INDICATORS						
Indicator	Value Chains					
	Powder Detergent	Automotive Components	Food Trays Manufacturing	Coffee Capsules	Packaging of Liquid Shampoo	Plastic Bags
Product Mass	Mass of new box 4 g lower than conventional one.	-	Mass of trays increases by 33% in innovation.	Mass of capsules increases by 33% in innovation.	Mass of shampoo bottle increases by 1% in innovation.	Mass of bags increases by 29% in innovation.
LFI	Recycling is enabled. Unrecoverable waste amount is decreased. LFI can be decreased.	Recycling is improved. Unrecoverable waste amount is decreased. LFI can be decreased.	Composting is a new EoL option. Since composted waste amount increases, unrecoverable waste amount sent to landfill decreases. By decreasing the mass of unrecoverable waste sent to landfill, mass of unrecoverable waste associated with a product also decreases. Therefore, LFI can be decreased.			
Compostable Rate	Since the coating is not compostable, there is no compostable rate.	There is no compostable rate due to use of fossil based plastic.	The rate increases due to use of biobased compostable plastic.			
Waste	Unrecoverable waste amount is decreased.	Unrecoverable waste amount is decreased.	Unrecoverable waste amount is decreased by composting.			

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4 REJECTION ANALYSIS

The analysis of the waste performed at the sorting plants is known as characterisation. It gives us information about the different material streams. Characterizations are normally been done at the entry of the plants to know, statistically, the composition of the waste deposited by the citizens at the containers. For this CIRC-PACK task, a set of characterisations has been done to know exactly the composition of the rejection fraction of the sorting plants.

Figure 20. Rejection fraction in sorting plants. Source: ECOEMBES

Disclaimer: all the data regarding the plants has been anonymized. All the characterisation analysis has been made in 35 different sorting plants inside Spain.

4.1 Characterisations methodology

Packaging waste characterisations in Spain have a standard that specifies the amount of waste selected for the sample (to ensure it is representative) and what must be measured and weighed during the characterisation process.

Waste characterisation consists of determining the composition of waste using a standardised test, controlling the error in the estimation of non-targeted material percentage with a 5% margin of error. The aim is to obtain a sample that is as homogeneous as possible on which to perform the sorting of material.

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The most regular and frequent characterisations in Spain are done on the entry to the sorting plants. For the Circ-Pack project, we have taken into account two different streams:

- End of line rejection
- Rejected thins (fines)

These first set of characterisations were made using the Spanish standards by ECOEMBES. The samples obtained were deposited on a clean, paved surface, in order to proceed to spread and homogenise them with a forklift. Material can be quartered if more than one person is doing the characterizations:

Figure 21. Quartered example in a characterisation. Source: ECOEMBES

Material sorting for characterisation was performed manually, weighing each fraction with a suitable calibrated/verified scale. It was verified that the materials were correctly selected.

The results obtained were recorded in the characterisation sheet, separated into requested and non-requested materials (see Figure 22.). The requested materials are domestic light packaging, and all other materials are regarded as not requested.

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LIGHT WEIGHT PACKAGING CHARACTERISATION SHEET

General data

Type of Characterisation:

Entry into Plant

Rejected waste from Plant

Date:

Agreement:

Entity: XXX

Characterisation Location: PS XXX

Characterisation Company: YYY S.A.

Characterisation Result:

Material	Quantity (kg)	% Weight
Requested materials (Packaging):		
PET	48,12	18,60
Natural HDPE	5,00	1,93
Colour HDPE	20,00	7,73
PVC	-	-
Film (except single-use bags)	15,00	5,80
Film single-use bags	10,00	3,87
Other plastics	35,00	13,53
Steel	30,00	11,60
Aluminium	2,85	1,10
Beverage carton	36,69	14,18
Wood	-	-
Unsolicited materials (*):		
Organic matter	10,12	3,91
Garden and pruning remains	0,08	0,03
Cellulose	0,04	0,02
Textiles	5,12	1,98
Wood non-packaging	-	-
Wood commercial/industrial packaging	-	-
Glass (containers)	3,14	1,21
Plastics non-packaging (except garbage bag film)	3,86	1,49
Garbage bag film	0,37	0,14
Plastics commercial/industrial packaging (except commercial/industrial film)	3,58	1,38
Commercial/industrial film	6,14	2,37
Debris from small works	-	-
Steel non-packaging	-	-
Steel commercial/industrial packaging	-	-
Aluminium non-packaging	-	-
Aluminium commercial/industrial packaging	-	-
Other (specify significant)	10,82	4,18
Paper/Cardboard:	6,37	2,46
Printed paper	3,78	1,46
Domestic packaging with Green Dot	1,47	0,57
Domestic packaging without Green Dot	1,12	0,43
Commercial packaging with Green Dot	-	-
Commercial packaging without Green Dot	-	-
Requested materials (Packaging):	202,66	78,35
Unsolicited materials (*):	56,01	21,65
Total	258,67	100,00

Observations:

Breakdowns in kg: (1) Other: Liquid contained in the packaging: 2.13 kg, Multimaterial: 1.86 kg Remains of medicines: 0.01 kg. RAEE: 2.11 kg, unclassifiable material that has been totally separated from the packaging fraction: 2.71 kg

(*): All materials that do not apply to household packaging of metal, plastic, wood or cardboard for drinks.

Figure 22. Spanish Characterisation Sheet. Source: Elaborated by ECOEMBES

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4.2 First sets of characterisations

Using the two initial sets (selected at random during the quartering phase), 77 characterisations were performed by Ecoembes (as described in Table 8).

Table 7. Initial sets of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Rejected flows	
Parameter	Details
End-of-line	53 characterizations
Thins	24 characterizations.
Period	All the samples were taken and analysed within 2019.
Country	All the samples were taken and analysed in sorting plants in Spain.
Sorting Plants	35 different sorting plants used for the samples

No characterisations were done for bulky items, as these do not fit within the scope of this work, with its focus on packaging items. As such, they were removed from rejected fraction as an unrequested material. To do so, once light packaging was placed on the feeder, bulky items were discharged to the primary triage conveyor belt where large or bulky material is removed (cardboard, film, etc.).

The information about all the characterisations done is just about weights and percentages separated by materials. Table 9 shows the results of the first characterisation, for both end-of-line and thins streams, broken down by percent of material present.

Table 8. Results initial sets of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Rejected flows Results First Characterisations						
Parameter	End-of-line			Thins		
	Avg. %	Min. %	Max. %	Avg. %	Min. %	Max. %
% Unrequested Materials	69.16	14.66	97.48	86.57	29.46	99.30
% Plastics: PET	3.01	0.00	17.79	0.27	0.00	1.45
% Plastics: Natural HDPE	0.09	0.00	0.73	0.04	0.00	0.22
% Plastics: HDPE Colour	0.72	0.00	8.61	0.80	0.00	6.03
% Plastics: PVC	0.01	0.00	0.18	0.01	0.00	0.07
% Plastics: Film (except single-use bags)	12.12	0.15	35.55	4.29	0.09	19.84
% Plastics: Film – single use bags	3.25	0.00	20.77	0.68	0.00	12.04
% Plastics: Other Plastics	7.17	0.08	39.41	5.92	0.08	45.61
% Metals: Steel	1.28	0.00	10.13	0.21	0.00	0.93
% Metals: Aluminium	0.87	0.00	6.84	0.72	0.00	6.93
% Beverage Carton	2.26	0.00	17.26	0.46	0.00	3.63
% Wood	0.06	0.00	1.38	0.02	0.00	0.17

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As we can see at the results above, the highest percentage (in terms of weight) are the unrequested materials. Therefore, we can confirm that the sorting-plants are selecting the packaging properly. The average of unrequested material for the thins (86.57%) is bigger than for the end-of line rejections (69.16%). In some characterisation, this unrequested material almost arrived to the 100% of the rejection.

For the end-of-line rejection, the most common requested material is films, followed by other plastics categories. For thins, the most common is other plastic followed by film. The lowest common plastic is PVC followed by natural HDPE in both characterisations. Wood and aluminium are not commonly found in the rejection fractions.

The unrequested materials represent the biggest fraction of the rejections in the Spanish sorting plants. Below, a breakdown of the results of all the materials for the first set of characterisations done for the Circ-Pack project related to end-of-line and thins can be found (Table 10):

Table 9. Break-down results (Unrequested Material) initial sets of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Rejected flows Unrequested Materials Results First Characterisations						
Parameter	End-of-line			Thins		
	Avg. %	Min. %	Max. %	Avg. %	Min. %	Max. %
% Organic Matter	3.11	0.00	35.84	2.42	0.00	25.13
% Garden and pruning remains	0.48	0.00	9.23	0.37	0.00	8.23
% Cellulose	15.84	0.12	38.48	8.16	0.31	34.69
% Textiles	10.44	0.15	29.26	1.40	0.00	12.49
% Wood non-packaging	0.96	0.00	20.25	0.12	0.00	1.95
% Wood commercial/industrial packaging	0.06	0.00	0.43	0.01	0.00	0.13
% Glass (containers)	0.89	0.00	6.87	2.03	0.00	14.20
% Plastics Non-packaging (except garbage bag film)	7.94	0.00	23.10	2.60	0.00	22.17
% Garbage bag film	1.64	0.00	37.70	0.19	0.00	4.19
% Plastics commercial/ industrial packaging (Except commercial/ industrial Film)	0.43	0.00	5.41	0.01	0.00	0.13
% Commercial/Industrial Film	0.50	0.00	8.27	0.59	0.00	8.27
% Debris from small works	0.33	0.00	3.41	0.01	0.00	0.26
% Steel non-packaging	0.27	0.00	3.12	0.12	0.00	0.76
% Steel commercial/industrial packaging	0.01	0.00	0.62	0.00	0.00	0.00
% Aluminium non-packaging	0.08	0.00	0.71	0.33	0.00	6.37
% Aluminium commercial/ industrial packaging	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
% Others	10.04	0.00	56.17	60.48	0.00	97.19

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% Printed paper	9.53	0.07	31.94	4.18	0.00	31.21
% Paper/Cardboard: domestic packaging with Green Dot	3.46	0.09	27.12	1.54	0.00	11.49
% Paper/Cardboard: domestic packaging without Green Dot	2.16	0.00	13.29	1.76	0.00	13.82
% Paper/Cardboard: commercial packaging with Green Dot	0.11	0.00	2.05	0.03	0.00	0.25
% Paper/Cardboard: commercial packaging without Green Dot	0.88	0.00	4.74	0.23	0.00	2.49

4.3 Second set of characterisations

With the results of the first sets of characterisations, some conclusions could be established, and initial calculations about the rejection items and extrapolations could be made. But these results were not enough to extract conclusions in terms of eco-design.

As such, new characterisations were performed with more focus on eco-design.

Table 10. Second set of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Rejected flows	
Parameter	Details
End-of-line	0 characterisations
Thins	4 characterisations.
Period	All the samples were taken and analysed within 2019.
Country	All the samples were taken and analysed in sorting plants in Spain.
Sorting Plants	4 different sorting plants used for the samples
Quantity	453.87 kgs. analysed

Figure 23. Thins fraction (characterisation). Source: ECOEMBES

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These new characterisations focused on eco-design, and analysed not only the materials but also:

- Colour (black, not black).
- Formats (bottles, caps, other formats)
- Sizes of the label
- Dimensions...

The method used for the characterisation was the one used in Ecoembes for this kind of characterisations: plants selected randomly, sampled selected randomly, manual separation of the sample by materials, analysis of every fraction (weigh, components, measure, pictures, labels, colours...)

Figure 24. Characterisation by material and end-use. Source: ECOEMBES

Table 11. Average Results of the second set of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Requested/ Unrequested	Material		Submaterial	Total %	
Requested Materials	Plastics PET	Bottles	Caps	0.0134	
			Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0.0137
				Not Wrapping label	0
		Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0.0308	
			Not Wrapping label	0.4708	
		Other formats	Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0
	Not Wrapping label			0.054	
	Not Black		Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
			Not Wrapping label	0.9386	
	Plastics HDPE Natural	Caps		0.0044	
Wrapping label >= 2/3		0.0209			
Not wrapping label		0.0249			

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	Plastics HDPE Colour	Bottles	Caps		0.0086	
			Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
				Not Wrapping label	0	
		Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0.0716		
			Not Wrapping label	0.0947		
		Other formats	Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
	Not Wrapping label			0.004		
	Not Black		Wrapping label >= 2/3	0		
			Not Wrapping label	0.2115		
	Plastics PVC	Bottles	Caps		0	
			Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
				Not Wrapping label	0	
			Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
		Not Wrapping label		0.0026		
		Other formats	Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
				Not Wrapping label	0	
			Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
	Not Wrapping label			0.0496		
	Plastics: Film (except single-use bags)					5.1204
	Plastics: Film – single use bags					1.0888
	Plastics: Film – labels without packaging (loose)					0.0837
	Plastics: Other Plastics	3D	Caps		0.002	
			Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0	
				Not Wrapping label	0	
Not Black			Wrapping label >= 2/3	0.1685		
		Not Wrapping label	0.1862			
2D		Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0		
			Not Wrapping label	0.3349		
		Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0.0075		
	Not Wrapping label		1.9323			
Plastics: loose caps					2.0446	
Metals: Steel					1.1457	
Metals: Aluminium					1.5224	
Beverage Carton	Caps		0.0088			
	Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0			
		Not Wrapping label	0.0088			
	Not Black	Wrapping label >= 2/3	0			
Not Wrapping label		0.5572				
Wood					0.0703	
Unrequested Materials					83.7037	

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From the analysis of these trials we can conclude that although certain containers are indeed found, there is no typology that stands out or predominates.

The main and most relevant conclusion is that the total amount of packaging present is much less than what was expected to be found.

It is also found packaging material, but it is usually fragmented, which will not allow us to make a direct comparison in terms of eco-design manoeuvres.

Packaging corresponding to the dairy derivatives sector (yogurts and similar) has not been found; packaging which has always been assumed to be collected in this part of the flow.

Among the small fraction collected, there is an important presence of capsules. This fact supports and justifies the developments done in this project, evaluating its transformation to compostable solutions.

In conclusion of this stage of characterizations and in order to meet the objective of being able to define eco-design measures, a third typology is proposed to analyse: material and concrete type of packaging format within those materials.

4.4 Third (and final) set of characterisations

A last set of characterisations was requested analysing the composition by format: yogurts, trays, caps... and for materials. The analysis has been done by complete packaging but also by pieces of packaging.

Table 12. Third set of characterisations. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Rejected flows	
Parameter	Details
End-of-line	0 characterisations
Thins	4 characterisations.
Period	All the samples were taken and analysed within 2019 until February 2020.
Country	All the samples were taken and analysed in sorting plants in Spain.
Sorting Plants	4 different sorting plants used for the samples
Quantity	465.78 kgs. analysed

The requested material for the last set of characterisations correspond to a 9.92% of the total amount of the rejection fraction divided in PET (0.11%), HDPE Natural (0.11%), HDPE Colour (0.71%), PVC (0%), Film (except single-use bags) (3.34%), Film – single use bags (0.2%), Other plastics (4.28%), Steel (0.41%), Aluminium (0.64%), Beverage Carton (0.07%), and Wood (0.05%).

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The PET packaging rejections include trays, blisters, bottles and lids:

Table 13. Rejected PET. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Figure 25. PET rejection examples. Source: ECOEMBES

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The **coloured HDPE** is one of the most rejected fractions (after the film) and includes tubes, pots, caps and single-dose packaging.

Table 14. Rejected HDPE. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

HDPE Natural		
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected	
Tube	0.004%	
Pot	0.077%	
Cap	0.004%	
Unit-dose	0.019%	
HDPE Colour		
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected	
Tube	0.088%	
Pot	0.077%	
Cap	0.537%	
Unit-dose	0.006%	

Figure 26. HDPE rejection examples. Source: ECOEMBES

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For the **PP** rejected fraction, most of the formats are caps followed by lids, capsules, various and caps:

Table 15. Rejected PP. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

PP	
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected
Cap	1.179%
Tub	0.045%
Lid	0.069%
Various	0.290%
Capsule	0.165%

Figure 27. PP rejection examples: caps, lids, pots and unit-dose. Source: ECOEMBES

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For the **polystyrene (PS)**, most of the rejected fractions are parts of trays following by tubs and yogurts:

Table 16. Rejected PS. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

PS	
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected
Tray	1.129%
Tub	0.002%
Yogurt	1.419%

Figure 28. Polystyrene rejection examples. Source: ECOEMBES

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Different formats of **films and bags** are rejected on the plants including labels, bags, laminated, wrappers and lids

Table 17. Rejected Film. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Film	
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected
Label	0.165%
Bag	0.721%
Laminated	0.021%
Wrapper	2.387%
Lid	0.047%

- Label
- Bag
- Laminated
- Wrapper
- Lid

Figure 29. Film rejection examples: bags, wrappers and aluminium-based bags. Source: ECOEMBES

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Regarding the **aluminium**, several formats of packaging are rejected by plants: tubes, trays, tubs, caps, lids, capsules and cans:

Table 18. Rejected Aluminium. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Figure 30. Aluminium rejection examples: tubs and caps. Source: ECOEMBES

Figure 31. Aluminium rejection examples: tubes, lids and capsules. Source: ECOEMBES

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The last rejected fractions are **steel** (just lids, bottle caps and cans) and **wood** (including caps and boxes).

Table 19. Rejected Steel. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Steel	
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected
Lid	0.279%
Bottle cap	0.127%
Cans	0.006%

Table 20. Rejected Wood. Source: Elaborated by Ecoembes

Wood	
Packaging format:	Percentage of the total rejected
Cap	0.043%
Boxes	0.002%

The results are analysed and it is concluded that among packaging found in the rejected fraction, the most prominent are the caps, whose impact will be minimized by the directive (EU) 2019/904 where in its article 6 express that single-use plastic products that have caps and lids made of plastic may be placed on the market only if the caps and lids remain attached to the containers during the products' intended use stage.

Regarding flexible packaging found (such as labels, bags, laminated, wrappers and lids), a change of material wouldn't avoid the fragmentation that makes them to be at this stage of the sorting process.

Caps, as well as the lids, should be designed in such a way that they remain attached to the main body after their use and disposal.

Once again it is important to highlight the relevance of transform the capsules in compostable.

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5 ECO-DESIGN RECOMMENDATIONS FOR REJECTED FRACTION'S MINIMIZATION

Eco-design strategies aim to create closed loop design by slowing resource loops or closing the resource loops. Eco-design and product innovation complement each other to improve industry's competitive position and increasing its sustainability practices. A sustainable product innovation addresses social (people), environmental (plant) and economic (profit) components of a value chain and identifies different types of impacts on each basic component.

Eco-design principles embedded in CIRC-PACK innovations are as follows,

- Decreased use of fossil-based sources,
- Introduction of circularity to a linear value chain,
- Valorization of a by-product or recycled product of the value chain,
- Enhanced end-of-life (EoL) properties,
- Addressing social acceptance of the improvements introduced.

Section 5 specifically focuses on the eco-design recommendations for the rejected packaging waste. Key barriers in packaging design are summarized in the table below. Section 5.1 discusses how relevant points from Table 22 could be addressed by the CIRC-PACK innovations introduced by the Demo Case A and Demo Case B. Furthermore, Section 5.2 discusses other type of eco-design recommendations could be addressed to decrease the amount of the rejected portion.

Table 21. Key barriers in packaging design (Hestin et al., 2017)

High Diversity of Products	
Intrinsic complexity of specific materials (e.g. Multilayer packaging) coupled with the high diversity of the composition of the waste flows	<p>Pet bottles vs pet trays: It is difficult to treat PET bottles together with trays due to differences on the additives and forming process.</p> <p>Small format packaging and multi-material packaging: Small format (lids and tear-offs and multi-material packaging is difficult to sort, economically unviable to recycle and is usually disposed of.</p> <p>Infrequently used resins: Sorting and recycling of uncommon resins (e.g.; PS, PVC, PLA, multilayers etc.) is in general very difficult due to technical limitations. In addition, their presence in the waste packaging flows results in a contamination of PET and polyolefin recyclates.</p> <p>Highly nutrient-contaminated packaging: Similar issues of infrequently used resins are faced when packaging contains high levels of organic nutrients, e.g. Fast-food packaging, which degrade the quality of recyclates.</p>

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	Dark and black products: Dark and black plastics, especially those containing specific dyers such as carbon black, rays are absorbed and cannot be identified in the sorting process.
Combination of several resins and grades within a single product with the use of imbricated (e.g. multilayer) or non-separable plastics (e.g. food bricks, flexible flasks)	Multilayer packaging in general contains polyamides or Ethylene Vinyl Alcohol (EVOH). These substances, if present in the recyclates, can result in an unintentional coloring of PET products and change their chemical, physical and mechanical properties.
High level of impurity in some flows caused by the mixing of different waste streams (e.g. food packaging and organic residues, agriculture waste, packaging in residual waste flows)	The quality of recyclates might be unpredictably affected due to incompatible resins or grades of resins. Especially in the case of grains, the optical brighteners and UV stabilisers can impact sorting process, since these substances affect the functioning of optical beams.
Strong Legislative, Marketing and Technical Requirements	
Food contact legal requirements	This matter currently affects mostly the PET bottle-to-bottle schemes even if gradually the uptake of rPET ¹ in food-related applications is growing. Other recycled resins (e.g. HDPE and LDPE) currently having a limited use in food-contact packaging are also affected to a larger extent. The requirements are set by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and affect all products put on the EU market.
Technical requirements covering mechanical, colour and physical properties	Technical requirements during the processes below affects recycling process directly, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The shaping processes (e.g. injection moulding and extrusion) of non-food packaging: Different properties and melting points of recycled plastics might cause cross-contamination, procedural complications and variations that might affecting part quality. • The manufacturing of black products, particularly when it concerns the production of dark black products:

¹ rPET= recycled PET or Polyethylene terephthalate

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	<p>Dark black colour is difficult to achieve with recyclates making it harder to achieve the desired colour properties during the manufacturing process;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The manufacturing of fibers: While using recyclates for fiber manufacturing, achieving a low level or complete absence of pollutants to maintain the desired mechanical and physical properties should be ensured. • The manufacturing of parts used in the automotive and construction industries: Considering especially the security standards, the used recyclates should demonstrate and ensure high durability and any other specific mechanical property required by the concerned manufacturing process.
The complexity of resins and the diversity of plastic products often impose difficulties in demonstrating compliance with specific requirements	Affected by the fact that improvements in waste management and technological developments do not always fulfill the requirements, since the end-users are continuously demanding better sorting, less odour and optimized colour to satisfy their customers.

5.1 Eco-design recommendations applying project developments

This section discusses the relevance of application of the Project developments obtained from Demo Case A and B for the rejected portion of the sorting plants. Ecodesign relevant innovations of the Demo Case A (biobased and compostable plastics) and Demo Case B (bio-based recyclable multimaterial formats and substitution of multilayer products by compostable layers) summarized in the table below.

Table 22. Eco-design Relevant Innovations of the Demo Case A and B

DEMO CASE A: Decoupling plastics from fossil feedstock by using alternative renewable feedstock.	
INNOVATION 1	New generation of bio-based and compostable materials with enhanced functionalities, in comparison with current non degradable materials, while guaranteeing properties in line with final products requirements, in relation to barrier, resistance to temperature variations, physical strength or biodegradability

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INNOVATION 3	It is a fact that most of the packaging (mainly film and trays) in direct contact with food is not properly sorted. To solve this problem, new bio-based material is produced. This material with biodegradable/compostable behaviour will allow managing this plastic waste in the same way than organic waste, making out the most of its nutrients content.
INNOVATION 4	Novel formulations for compounding based on recycled biomaterials have been demonstrated in the recyclability of biobased materials for bags production.
Demo Case B: Creation of innovative formats and testing materials that improve recyclability and the end-of-life scenario.	
INNOVATION 1	Fully bio-based multilayer structures serving various (barrier) functionalities that are fully compatible with the majority of the existing paper and board recycling processes preventing the current stream of mixed paper/plastic waste
INNOVATION 2	Compostable bio-based materials developed in DC-A in combination with current commercial compostable material have been tested in new optimized formulations for achieving similar performance of current nor compostable, neither recyclable, multilayer solutions.

Within the scope of Demo Case A, sorting and recyclability of new biomaterials and biopackaging, and adaptation of current recycling protocols have been studied. Demo Case A demonstrates the sorting efficiency and purity of bioplastic bottles (Value Chain 3), bioplastic trays (Value Chain 5) and bio-based shopping bags (Value Chain 4). Hence, only those three goods and the progress achieved in their value chain is considered for further eco-design conclusions in this section. Below the purity and effectiveness level for the sorting of the aforementioned three value chain is given including the benchmark good to which the innovation is compared. Please note that this data is directly from the Deliverable 3.4 Report and already discussed in more detail in Section 3 of this report. It is possible to reach 100% effectiveness only for the sorting of bio-based shopping bags with bioplastic presence of 3%. Lastly, the introduced optical sorting enables to differentiate packaging from its labels, sleeves as well as caps attached to it that eventually are made of other materials.

Table 23. Sorting efficiency of the biomaterial used in the Demo Case A

Innovation	Benchmark Good	Bioplastics Presence 3%		Bioplastics Presence 10%		Bioplastics Presence 15%	
	Benchmark Good	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)
Bioplastic bottles	PET Bottle	96.81	81.25	96.54	84.29	98.02	81.95
Bioplastic trays	PE or PET	95.58	96.43	98.20	98.80	96.68	96.39
Bio-based shopping Bags	LDPE and HDPE	95.24	100.00	92.96	97.06	84.75	98.04

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Considered the above-mentioned sorting results, possible points to be addressed with the second set of characteristics are listed below:

- Introduction of bioplastic bottles within the sorting system can address the rejected plastic pet bottles not black both with wrapping label and not wrapping label which constitutes 0.5016% of the rejected portion on average,
- As stated in the Section 5.2, not using dark colours leads to an increased efficiency in the sorting. Merging it with the capability of the sorting innovation which differentiating the material even with the wrapping, it is possible to address plastic PET black bottles both with and without wrapping. Using the non-black coloured bioplastic bottles, it is possible to address plastic PET black bottles both with and without wrapping which constitutes 0.0137% of the rejected portion on average,
- Biobased shopping bags can address the plastic film-single use bags that are rejected and constitutes 1.0888 % of the rejected portion on average.

Please remark that above given percentages only reflects the percentage of the material/product in the rejected portion. This does not mean that all of the products are substituted with 100% replacement rate. To discuss replacement percentage with the newly developed biopolymer, we need more technical data on sorting such as the percentage of bioplastic presence.

The third set of characterisation has the data on composition format along with its materials. On the other hand, Innovations from Demo Case A focusing on sorting and recyclability of new biomaterials and biopackaging, and adaptation of current recycling protocols do not include improvements in format. Hence, the third characterisation is not further analysed in relation to Demo Case A.

Innovations from Demo Case A alone does not address any of the rejected portion from the HDPE rejections, even though the coloured HDPE is one of the most rejected fractions after the film. Another restriction is on PS trays. PS trays could not be addressed the biopolymers developed which are benchmarked with PE or PET, but not with PS.

Within the scope of Demo Case B; collection, sorting and recyclability of multimaterial and multi-layered products are studied. Demo Case B demonstrates the sorting efficiency and purity of multimaterial cardboard packaging (CIRC-PACK Value Chain 2) and food packaging trays (CIRC-PACK Value Chain 5). Hence, only those two goods and the advancement achieved in their value chain is considered for further eco-design conclusions in this section.

In the Deliverable 4.4 Report, Demo Case B argues that multi-layered trays proposed in this project would end up in the same fraction as the mono-layer trays. Hence, sorting tests of Demo Case A also take into account multi-layered trays implying that there are no additional sorting results on food packaging trays coming from Demo Case B. On the other hand, Demo Case B additionally argues that the position of multi-layered packaging going through optical sorter affects its classification by the sorter as multi-layered or monolayer packaging. If multi-layered tray goes through the optical sorter upside down, the optical sorter classifies it as mono-layer tray. If the multi-layered tray goes through the optical sorter face up with entire or partially broken sheet, the optical sorter will classify it as multi-layered

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tray. In both cases, the tray is still sorted and not rejected. Hence, this aspect has no impact on addressing the rejected portion focused in Section 4.

Another factor that might affect the detection of trays as multi-layered or monolayer packaging is the opaqueness of the cover, i.e. film layer. If the cover is not opaque enough to enable to extract spectral information from the tray, the tray could be treated as a multi-layered packaging. If the cover is opaque, only the film covering the tray is detected by the sensor. Then, any other film packaging such as bio-based plastic bags exist in the stream would be likely to be classified along with trays. Again, this aspect has no impact on addressing the rejected portion. However, to address proper sorting of multi-layered trays for recycling purposes, decreasing the opaqueness of the film layer in an attempt to detect below laying tray is an eco-design aspect that needs to be further considered.

The multilateral packaging analysed in Demo Case B is PE-laminated cardboard detergent boxes. BUMAGA provided paperboard A3 sheets with bio-based additives as barrier, which was validated by SAPONIA. Efficiency of the optical sorter aiming the sorting of bio multi-material packaging from paper/cardboard flow is summarized below (Deliverable 4.4). 100% efficiency in sorting is found to be only possible when the presence of bio multi-material packaging is 3%. Purity and efficiency percentage decrease is correlated with the increased percentage of the presence of bio multi-material packaging. However, Demo Case B concludes that optical sorter could be set up sacrificing purity for effectiveness or vice versa depending on recovery criteria.

Table 24. Sorting efficiency of the bio multi-material packaging used in the Demo Case B

Innovation	Bioplastics Presence 3%		Bioplastics Presence 5%		Bioplastics Presence 10%	
	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)	Purity (%)	Effectiveness (%)
Bio multimaterial cardboard packaging	92.41	100	88.43	95.54	86.54	93.30

Unlike Demo Case A, which is more addressed with second set of rejection analysis data, multimaterial cardboard packaging of Demo Case B can be addressed only with first set of the rejection data. The aforementioned data set includes the rejected percentage of both paper/cardboard for domestic and commercial packaging with or without Green Dot. Since the product of Demo Case B is packaging for powder detergent, it is assumed to cover only domestic paper/cardboard packaging with or without Green Dot. Relatedly, below mentioned points could be further addressed thanks to Demo Case B,

- For the end-of-line rejection, on average 5.62% of the total rejected material is domestic paper/cardboard with or without Green Dot. Introduction of bio multi-material cardboard packaging could address some extend of this rejected portion considering the fact that the innovated multimaterial could be used to replace the cardboard laminated with plastic or other that needs barrier properties.
- For the rejected thins, on average 3.30% of the total rejected material is domestic paper/cardboard with or without Green Dot. Similarly to the end-of-line rejection, introduction of bio multi-material cardboard packaging could address this rejected

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portion. The portion without Green Dot alone constitutes 1.76% percent on average within the rejected thins.

Based on the noted shortcomings of innovations of Demo A and Demo B, further eco-design recommendations are included under section 5.2 to discuss additional eco-design options to address the rejected portion.

5.2 Other type of eco-design recommendations

Thanks to the analysis done of the rejection fraction, some recommendations has been proposed during the conclusions on that analysis:

- Small packaging like blisters, single-dose, capsules, etc. should be designed with clearly identifiable compostable material and must be thrown away with the rest of the organic waste.
- Also the recommendation for the seals or lids / safety films of some food containers, that should be designed to avoid the fact to be separated from the main container, or should be redesigned to avoid that parts, or make them compostable to be placed together with the organic waste directly.
- The caps / lids, clearly indicated to be deposited together with the bottle, or which cannot be separated from the terrines.

Also, find here some eco-design recommendation to allow the packaging to be selected at the sorting plants:

- Smaller labels promote detection of the main packaging material. We recommend label dimensions less than 2/3 of the packaging surface, in the same material as the body of the packaging and avoiding black and metallic colours.
- It is recommended that packaging dimensions will be adjusted to less than 300 mm so that they are guided through the proper process flows.
- Packages with flat, unfilmiform morphology can be driven by erroneous flows during the process. If possible, the size ratio should be greater than 2 cm.
- Metallic colours can cause errors in detection systems. It is recommended that the surface or labels having these characteristics occupy a surface less than 2/3 of the packaging surface. It is also recommended to be of the same material as the packaging body and to avoid black and metallic colours.
- Metallic packaging with planar morphology can be driven by erroneous flows during the process. Manual selection makes it difficult to distinguish between steel and aluminium and it is therefore recommended that indications on the material type be placed on the packaging. If possible, the size ratio should be greater than 5 cm.
- Package with dimensions less than 50 mm can be driven by the flow of fine materials and not be selected. It is recommended to evaluate the possibility of a different dimensional configuration of the packaging solution.
- The current technology used in sorting plants does not allow black to be detected, so it is recommended to use alternative designs that can improve the visibility of these containers.

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5.3 Waste Prevention Assessment of Eco-design Techniques Applied to Rejected Fraction

In this section, potential reductions in the amount of landfilled or incinerated waste are evaluated by taking into consideration the results and recommendations of eco-design techniques studied under Task 6.1.1 and Task 6.1.2. In Chapter 5.1 and 5.2, eco-design recommendations were stated according to project developments and other types of developments, respectively.

Ecoembes worked on current situation of rejected packaging waste amounts. According to 18 plants results, characterization of rejected materials is as given in Table 25. The results present current situation of Spain. As shown in the table, film of single use bags, PET, HDPE colour, natural HDPE and wood had respectively 0.68%, 0.27%, 0.08%, 0.04% and 0.02% in the total rejected waste amount. These rejected materials are studied materials within the scope of CIRC-PACK.

Table 25. Sorting rejection characterization results of thins performed by Ecoembes

Rejected Material	Average %
PET	0.27
Natural HDPE	0.04
HDPE Colour	0.08
PVC	0.01
Film (except single-use bags)	4.29
Film (single use bags)	0.68
Other plastics	5.92
Metals (steel)	0.21
Metals (aluminium)	0.72
Beverage carton	0.46
Wood	0.02

Sorting efficiency results performed by CALAF show that although purity and effectiveness of bioplastic trays are respectively around 95.58% and 96.43%, effectiveness of biobased bottles is notably lower as 81.25% because of their morphology. According to second set of characterization data provided by Ecoembes, currently 0.5016% of rejected plastic PET bottles not black both with wrapping label and not wrapping label can be addressed by using new sorting system for biobased bottles. Therefore, this amount can no longer be sent to landfill or incineration facilities. The amount of waste can be sent to composting facility or recycling. By these new EoL options, this waste amount can be regained to economy.

As stated in the section 5.1 and 5.2, dark coloured usage (black and metallic colours) in the packaging materials cause decrease in sorting efficiency. Avoiding the use of dark colours and using new sorting system for biobased plastics, 0.0137% of rejected waste parts can be successfully sorted, so this amount can be addressed as decreased landfilled and incinerated waste PET bottle amount.

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According to the result of sorting of biobased shopping bags, sorting efficiencies change in between 98.04% and 100% depending on bioplastic presence percentage. Since higher sorting efficiency of new biobased plastic bag was obtained, currently rejected portion of 1.0888% can be addressed as not sent to landfill or incineration.

In Table 4, the result of sorting of bioplastic waste is given. Depending on effectiveness values, rejection percentages were calculated. In the second set of characterization, rejected plastic film portion was addressed as 1.0888% in the total rejected waste amount. With new sorting system and biobased plastic application, 100% sorting efficiency can be obtained. Therefore, there is no rejected waste amount sent to landfill or incineration.

In the result of multi-material packaging waste sorting stated in D4.4, effectiveness of 3%, 5% and 10% bio multi-material packaging are given as 100%, 95.54% and 93.30%, respectively. It was stated that the lower the presence of target material at entrance of optical sorter is, the higher the optical sorter performance. Sortability and recyclability of new multi-material packaging has been improved depending on selective collection and sorting. Therefore, new multi-material packaging waste can be sorted by higher effectiveness and recycling performance. In baseline, PE laminate hinders the paper recycling process. With the new innovation, recycling of this type of packaging waste can be provided, since the PE laminate is replaced by a dispersion coating which is compatible with current recycling processes. According to end-of-line rejection characterization, average 5.62% of the total rejected material can be addressed by new multi-material packaging design. In the rejected thins results, 3.30% of the total rejected material can be addressed by new multi-material packaging design. In current situation, multi-material packaging waste in powder detergent value chain is not recycled due to presence of PE and cardboard. Landfilled amount of this value chain packaging waste can be decreased by innovations. Therefore, mentioned rejected characterization percentage can be addressed for the amount of new applicable EoL options.

According to the result of multi-layered packaging waste sorting stated in D4.4 and in D3.4, effectiveness was found as higher than 96% for trays. With new optical devices, multi-layered packaging waste can be distinguished from mono-layered packaging waste. However, packaging material should be face up through optical sorter. Therefore, it is assumed that this requirement is provided during saving assessment. Use of the devices contributes to sending of it to composting processes when recycling of it is not possible. Because of these, lower amount of multi-layered packaging waste can be sent to landfill or incineration.

It is stated in eco-design recommendations that small packaging materials should be designed with clearly identifiable compostable material and must be thrown away with the rest of the organic waste. By developing new design through the recommendation, composting of plastic packaging waste can be increased due to less rejection of these waste types in sorting stage.

When safety films used in some food containers can be redesigned as compostable, separation of films and trays can be avoided and these waste types can be thrown away with organic waste. With this application, food tray packaging waste types can have added value by sending to composting facility rather than landfill.

During detection of packaging materials, smaller labels were stated as effective detectable compared to larger ones. Therefore, rejection of them during sorting processes can be

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decreased by avoiding dark colours and using label with the dimension less than 2/3 of the packaging surface. Recycling of packaging materials can be increased by applying these recommendations.

It is highlighted that the End of Life stage has been identified as crucial for a good degree of performance of the CIRC-PACK value chain, as assessed by the application of the CEIS framework of indicators. It is not even excluded that for some specific value chains, the End of Life route is determinant in guaranteeing the sustainability of the whole chain.

From this perspective, the sorting efficiency at plant plays an important role towards the improvement of the waste management process, starting, in general terms, from the sorting at consumers and finishing with the preparation of treated waste for conversion into secondary raw materials.

In addition, the recycling rate – quantitatively influenced by the efficiency of the sorting process – is considered as one of the relevant national based factors to assess the replicability of circular economy-based schemes in the wide sector of plastic product and plastic packaging specifically.

Precisely, the waste collection and separation capacity is selected as criteria to evaluate the potential for replicability with a country/region. The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other waste) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

As a result of an internal consultation of the CIRC-PACK partners, it emerged that the majority of the interviewed partners considered the waste collection and separation capacity of high importance for the successful implementation of circular economy schemes in the plastic sector, also highlighting a high priority in comparison to other typical drivers. However, it was also pointed out that this aspect should be coupled with the capacity of treating not only large amounts of waste, but also a large variety of waste fractions, even though technical risks may unfortunately overwhelm the sorting efficiency and capacity. To compensate this latter aspect, a standard communication of the specific properties of each material should be pursued.

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6 CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of this report was to analyse the potential impacts that the innovative solutions proposed by the CIRC-PACK Demo Cases have in terms of waste prevention, recycling rates and landfill storage.

The recycling of packaging is a technologically driven process composed of several stages. The collection systems in place, and the configuration and infrastructure used by different sorting plants, has an impact on the effective capture of materials, and the amount of materials which are leaked ('the rejected fraction'). By mapping the process of the Spanish sorting plants in detail, possible points of rejection can be identified. This was then compared to other collection-model sorting plants in Europe.

Then, a literature review was conducted, in order to survey waste prevention and circular economy relations, develop a quantification methodology for waste prevention, review indicators for evaluating waste prevention actions, and research EoL options for plastics and biobased plastics. Change in sorting efficiency was evaluated. While lower sorting effectiveness was achieved in biobased plastic waste for bottles, higher effectiveness was obtained in biobased trays and films. However, purity showed a change according to value chains and presence of biobased plastic waste. In general, higher purity was observed in three value chains of CIRC-PACK innovation except for films with presence of 10% biobased plastic waste. The specific impacts of innovative packaging products developed through CIRC-PACK were assessed. It was found that:

- Powder detergent boxes: by switching from conventional PE laminated cardboard boxes to the CIRC-PACK innovation, the amount of waste paperboard sent to landfill sites is reduced as 12%, and amount being sent for incineration reduced as 12.6%. Recycling is suitable option by changing packaging material. According to LCA results, recycling of CIRC-PACK boxes is the best scenario.
- Automotive components: PP waste is recycled rather than landfill or incineration by applying CIRC-PACK innovation. Internally recycling in CRF facility is aimed in CIRC-PACK.
- Food trays manufacturing: when incineration of baseline and biobased waste is compared, it is seen that 30.41 g more waste is incinerated. Composting and biopolymer recycling are different EoL options compared to baseline due to biobased polymer usage in CIRC-PACK innovation. According to LCA results, approximately 40% environmental improvement is achieved by using biopolymers in trays. Recycling and composting are stated as the best options.
- Coffee capsules: by switching from conventional coffee capsules to CIRC-PACK innovation, incineration and landfill options are reduced to 17.6% and 22.4%, respectively. LCA results show that environmental preferability of new coffee capsules is more than traditional one.
- Liquid shampoo bottles: there is 1% increase in the weight of shampoo bottle by using biopolymer. Composting is one of the EoL options due to biopolymer use in CIRC-PACK. According to LCA results, lower impact is obtained by composting

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bioplastics compared to fossil based one. Environmental impact can be reduced up to 48% by recycling biobased bottle.

- Plastic bags: weight of new biopolymer bags is 29% higher than PELD bags. Landfilling, recycling and incineration are considered as EoL options for fossil-based bags. Composting is included in addition to baseline options due to biobased compostable material use. LCA results show that incineration of new thin bags is the worst option. On the other hand, impacts due to landfilling and composting are similar. By recycling, important environmental improvement is provided because of reduction in new biopolymer production.

In order to evaluate why certain materials are rejected from the recycling process, a series of waste characterisations were performed on two rejection faction streams (from the end-of-line and film streams) at the Spanish sorting plant.

It was found that the largest percentage (in terms of weight) of rejected materials were 'unrequested materials' (i.e. materials which have been disposed of in the wrong bin, and which cannot be recycled in the plant). In some characterisations, this made up to as much of 100% of the rejected materials.

The most common requested material to be rejected was films, followed by other plastic categories. PVC and HDPE, on the other hand, makes up the lowest contribution to the rejection faction.

When examining the rejected faction according to eco-design principles, it was found there is no typology that stands out or predominates, which hampers the assessment. There is packaging material but it is usually fragmented, which will not allow us to make a direct comparison in terms of eco-design manoeuvres. No packaging has been found corresponding mainly to the dairy derivatives sector (yoghurt and similar), which has always been assumed to be lost in this part of the flow. There is an important presence of coffee capsules.

Finally, the format of the materials being rejected was analysed. It was found that the presence of packaging the most prominent are the caps; that with the new European directive this phenomenon will be minimized. Flexible packaging, a change of material is no guarantee that there is no fragmentation that causes them to be at this stage of the selection so other possible actions will have to be analysed. Caps, as well as the lids should try to get them attached to the main body. And once again, highlighting the relevance of the capsules as an option to adopt compostable materials.

Based on the above evaluation, a range of eco-design recommendations are discussed. Eco-design strategies aim to slow and close resource loops. In CIRC-PACK, relevant eco-design principles includes: decreased use of fossil-based sources; the introduction of circularity to a linear value chain; valorisation of by-products or related products; enhanced EoL properties; and ensuring social acceptance of new innovative materials.

Key barriers are discussed, such as the diversity of products, including: the intrinsic complexity of specific materials coupled with the high diversity of materials present in the waste flow; the combination of several resins and grades within a single product; the high level of impurities in some flows, caused by mixing different waste streams. In addition, legislative requirements around food-grade plastics, and the technical requirements for

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achieving packaging needs and meeting consumer expectations are further factors to be considered in product design.

CIRC-PACK Demo Case A demonstrates that use of biobased and compostable plastics which are developed within the Demo can address below points which might target the rejected materials during sorting,

- bioplastic bottles with the developed sorting system can address the rejected plastic pet bottles both black and not black, and both with and without wrapping label,
- biobased shopping bags can address the plastic film-single use bags,
- conventional PET use for trays and bottles can be addressed by the bioplastic bottles and bioplastic trays developed.

To discuss replacement percentage with the newly developed biopolymer and state that the rejection ratio of the concerned product will be lower, we need more technical data on sorting such as the percentage of bioplastic presence. Furthermore, innovations from Demo Case A alone does not address the fraction of HDPE rejections, even though the coloured HDPE is one of the most rejected fractions after the film. Another restriction is on PS trays. PS trays could not be addressed the biopolymers developed which are benchmarked with PE or PET, but not with PS.

CIRC-PACK Demo Case B – which developed innovative bio-based multilayer structures – can address rejected portion of domestic paper/cardboard with or without Green Dot, including both rejected thins and end-of-line rejection. In addition, Demo Case B argues that multi-layered trays proposed in this project would end up in the same fraction as the mono-layer trays. Even though the rejected portion is not affected, position of multi-layered packaging going through optical sorter changes its classification by the sorter as multi-layered or monolayer packaging which later on alters the recycling process. Another factor might affect the detection of trays as multi-layered or monolayer packaging is the opaqueness of the cover, i.e. film layer. To address proper sorting of multi-layered trays for recycling purposes, decreasing the opaqueness of the film layer in an extend to detect below laying tray is an eco-design aspect that needs to be further considered.

Finally, the potential reductions in the amount of landfilled or incinerated waste which could be achieved through the introduction of CIRC-PACK innovations was evaluated. According to eco-design recommendations, savings were specified as follows:

- According to characterization data provided by Ecoembes, currently 0.5016% of rejected plastic PET bottles not black both with wrapping label and not wrapping label can be addressed for composting or recycling EoL options rather than landfill or incineration.
- With not using dark colours and using new sorting system for biobased plastics, 0.0137% of rejected waste parts can be successfully sorted, so this amount can be addressed as decreased landfilled and incinerated waste PET bottle amount.
- Since higher sorting efficiency of new biobased plastic bag was obtained, currently rejected portion of 1.0888% can be addressed as not sent to landfill or incineration.
- Sortability and recyclability of new multi-material packaging has been improved depending on selective collection and sorting. Therefore, new multi-material

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packaging waste can be sorted by higher effectiveness and recycling performance. According to end-of-line rejection characterization, average 5.62% of the total rejected material can be addressed by new multi-material packaging design. In the rejected thins results, 3.30% of the total rejected material can be addressed by new multi-material packaging design. These rejected amounts can be sorted and recycled by CIRC-PACK innovations.

- Effectiveness was found as higher than 96% for trays as multi-layered packaging waste. With new optical devices, multi-layered packaging waste can be distinguished from mono-layered packaging waste. Because of these, lower amount of multi-layered packaging waste can be sent to landfill or incineration.
- Composting of plastic packaging waste can be increased by designing small packaging materials and films of food containers as compostable.
- Recycling of packaging materials can be increased by applying smaller labels on packaging surface.

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8 ANNEXES

8.1 ANNEX A: Inventory Data of Waste Prevention Assessment

Powder Detergent Value Chain

In Table 27, Table 28 and Table 29, change in the amount of waste according to EoL options is shown for power detergent value chain.

Table 26. EoL scenarios of baseline for powder detergent

EoL Scenario (Baseline)			
PE Laminated Boxes			
Box Primary Packaging		Box Secondary Packaging	Plastic Film
97% Landfill	3% Incineration	100% Recycling	100% Recycling
Waste Paperboard (g)	Waste PE (g)	Cardboard Boxes (g)	PE (g)
33.31	1.03	15.51	0.26
Starch Coated Boxes			
Plastic Film Palletizing		Waste Paperboard	
100% Recycling		90% Recycling	10% Landfill
Cardboard Boxes (g)	PE (g)	Paperboard (g)	Paperboard (g)
15.51	0.26	0.306	0.034

Table 27. EoL scenarios of innovation for powder detergent

EoL Scenario (Innovation)			
PE Laminated Boxes			
Box Primary Packaging		Box Secondary Packaging	Plastic Film
97% Landfill	3% Incineration	100% Recycling	7% Recycling
Waste Paperboard (g)	Waste PE (g)	Cardboard Boxes (g)	PE (g)
29.10	0.90	370	0.0184

Table 28. EoL scenarios change between baseline and innovation

EoL Scenario (Change)			
PE Laminated Boxes			
Box Primary Packaging		Box Secondary Packaging	Plastic Film
97% Landfill	3% Incineration	100% Recycling	100% and 7% Recycling
Waste Paperboard	Waste PE	Cardboard Boxes	PE

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EoL Scenario (Change)			
PE Laminated Boxes			
Box Primary Packaging		Box Secondary Packaging	Plastic Film
97% Landfill	3% Incineration	100% Recycling	100% and 7% Recycling
(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)
- 4.21	- 0.13	354.49	- 0.24

Automotive Components Value Chain

In Table 30, Table 31 and Table 32, change in the amount of waste according to EoL options is shown for automotive components value chain.

Table 29. EoL scenarios of baseline for automotive components

EoL Scenario (Baseline)				
Polypropylene				
100% Incineration		100% Landfill		100% Recycling
Waste PP (g)	Waste Glass (g)	Waste PP (g)	Inert Waste (g)	PP (g)
830	170	830	170	1000

Table 30. EoL scenarios of innovation for automotive components

EoL Scenario (innovation)	
Polypropylene	
100% Recycling (50% in CRF and 50% in out)	100% Recycling (in CRF)
PP (g)	PP (g)
500	1000

Table 31. EoL scenarios change between baseline and innovation

EoL Scenario (Change)	
Polypropylene	
100% Recycling (50% in CRF and 50% in out)	100% Recycling (in CRF)
PP (g)	PP (g)
-500	0

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Food Trays Manufacturing Value Chain

In Table 33, Table 34 and Table 35 change in the amount of waste according to EoL options is shown for food trays value chain.

Table 32. EoL scenarios of baseline for food trays manufacturing

EoL Scenario (Baseline)									
Food Trays Manufacturing									
100% Recycling		40% Recycling and 60% Landfill				100% Incineration		100% Landfill	
PET (g)	PE (g)	PET recycling (g)	PE recycling (g)	PET landfill (g)	PE landfill (g)	PET (g)	PE (g)	PET (g)	PE (g)
33.4	2	13.36	0.8	20.4	1.2	3.4	2	33.4	2

Table 33. EoL scenarios of innovation for food trays manufacturing

EoL Scenario (Innovation)					
Food Trays Manufacturing					
100% Landfill		100% Composting		Biopolymer Recycling	100% Incineration
PET (g)	PE (g)	Biowaste (PET) (g)	Biowaste (PE) (g)	Biowaste (g)	Biowaste (g)
33.73	2.07	33.73	2.07	35.81	35.81

Table 34. EoL scenarios change between baseline and innovation

EoL Scenario (Change)					
Food Trays Manufacturing					
100% Landfill		100% Composting		Biopolymer Recycling	100% Incineration
PET (g)	PE (g)	Biowaste (PET) (g)	Biowaste (PE) (g)	Biowaste (g)	Biowaste (g)
0.33	0.07	33.73	2.07	0.41	30.41

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Coffee Capsule Value Chain

In Table 36 and Table 37 change in the amount of waste according to EoL options is shown for coffee capsules value chain.

Table 35. EoL scenarios of baseline for coffee capsules

EoL Scenario (Baseline)	
PP Capsules	
44% Incineration	56% Landfill
PP Capsule (g)	PP Capsule (g)
0.66	0.84

Table 36. EoL scenarios of innovation for coffee capsules

EoL Scenario (Change)		
PP Capsules		
60% Composting	17.6% Incineration	22.4% Landfill
PP Capsule (g)	PP Capsule (g)	PP Capsule (g)
1.2	-0.31	-0.40

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8.2 ANNEX B: Graphic Characterisation Example

Find here two complete examples of a complete Circ-Pack characterisation of a rejection fraction in one of the sorting plants in Spain:

Example 1:

Initial Checking Requested Unrequested

PET bottle PET blister HDPE N tube HDPE N pot

HDPE C tube HDPE C pot Film Film lid

Film single-use bags Nets PP caps 1PP pots

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PP lids

PP various

PS trays

PS yogurts

Aluminium tube

Aluminium Tube not drink

Aluminium tray

Aluminium tub

Aluminium lid

Aluminium capsules

Beverage carton

Organic matter

Cellulose

Textiles

Glass

Plastic non packaging

Aluminium non packaging

Electronic waste

Ceramic

Medicines

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Unclassifiable material

Paper/ cardboard pack

Example 2:

Initial

Characterization

Sample

Check

PET tray

HDPE N Unit-dose

HDPE C Caps

HDPE C tubes

HDPE C Caps

HDPE C Unit-dose

PVC

Film label

Film Labels

Film Wrappers

Film Laminated

Film Wrappers

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Film lids

Film lids

PP caps

PP caps

PP Tub

PS Trays

PP Lids

PS Others

PP Various

PP capsules

PS Trays

PS Yogurts

PS Others

Steel Bottle Caps

Steel Lids

Steel Bottle Caps

Steel Others

Steel Others

Aluminium Lids

Aluminium Capsules

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Aluminium others

Wood

Wood

Organic Matter

Organic Matter

Pruning rests

Cellulose

Cellulose

Textiles

Textiles

Wood

Glass

Glass

Plastic non packaging

Plastic non packaging

Steel non packaging

Aluminium non packaging

Aluminium non packaging

Printed paper

Solid liquid

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Multimaterial

Multimaterial

Medicines

Sanitary

Electronic waste

Glass Ceramic not packaging

Unclassifiable material

Doubt

Printed paper

Doubt